

COMPETENCE AND ITS ROLE IN THE ACTIVITY OF THE LEADER OF NON-GOVERNMENT NON-COMMERCIAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *The article describes the role of non-governmental non-profit organizations in the development of civil society, the problems of increasing the professional competence of non-governmental non-profit organization leaders and their role in society using information and communication technologies, and the conditions for improving the environment of information exchange.*

Keywords: *civil society, non-governmental non-profit organization, competence, competence, professional competence, competence modeling, professionogram, profile public control, communication, information exchange.*

One of the most important signs of the existence of civil society is the effectiveness of the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations and their legal status at the level of the state and society.

After all, our President Shavkat Mirziyoev did not point out for nothing that "all-round support for the activities of non-governmental organizations and civil society is the priority of effective management."

The goals and tasks aimed at increasing the role of non-governmental non-commercial organizations are defined in the development strategy.

The 43rd task of the state program for the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 in the year "Glorification of human value and active neighborhood" is called "Wide involvement of public control subjects in the process of implementation of certain state functions", reducing poverty, creating new jobs It is decided to introduce the practice of offering the implementation of socially useful projects to non-governmental non-commercial organizations based on an open competition.

Currently, the number of non-governmental non-profit organizations is about 10 thousand, and they are operating in one or another sphere of society. 1,955 non-governmental non-profit organizations are active in business support and farm development, 280 in women's protection, 220 in public health care, and 150 in education [1].

In the book "New Uzbekistan Strategy" by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoev, the process of supporting civil society institutions and non-governmental non-profit organizations in the implementation of the strategy of developing our country and building a New Uzbekistan is being accelerated, and in this respect, the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations and civil society institutions It was emphasized that comprehensive support is one of the priorities in the implementation of effective management.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6181 dated March 4, 2021 "On approval of the concept of civil society development in 2021-2025",

consistent improvement of the legal basis of civil society development, assistance to civil society institutions and the mechanism of their state support issues such as further improvement, further expansion of the participation of civil society institutions in the implementation of state and state social projects, and ensuring the openness of the activities of civil society institutions were defined.

In accordance with this Decree, the institution of permanent representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations participating in the meetings of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis and its committees (commissions) was introduced (hereinafter - permanent representative). [2]

In accordance with the decree, a total of 750 representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations will be trained by 2025, and in 2021, training aimed at improving the skills of leaders of non-governmental non-profit organizations began at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

These professional development courses are conducted on the basis of a special 72-hour curriculum. Certificates of the Academy of State Administration are provided to the trainees who have successfully completed the training. 100 trainees in 2022, and 150 trainees in 2023 improved their qualifications within the framework of such retraining and advanced training courses. It is planned to train 200 representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations in 2024 and 250 in 2025.

Leaders of non-governmental non-profit organizations who have improved their skills in the courses were attached to the "Staff of Trainers", and they organized 613 events in the regions and provided consultative support to 637 NGOs.

In order to develop drafts of legislative documents related to the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, prepare proposals for the improvement of regulatory legal documents and provide legal opinions, as well as provide consultative consulting services, the Association has established an "Expert Group" consisting of representatives of 112 non-governmental non-profit organizations with extensive experience in their field. done.

Nevertheless, it is important to create the necessary opportunities to increase the competence of leaders and employees of non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society and their business acumen, knowledge and experience, and to support activities in this regard.

The analysis of researches shows that the issues of improving the professional competence of personnel in the management of the state and society have been studied in different directions by foreign and domestic scientists in different periods.

In general, when studying the essence of the concepts of "competence" and "competence", the scientists emphasized that these concepts are used as similar, interrelated concepts and differ by their differential and integral features. In a number of scientific works, the psychological and pedagogical essence of the concepts of "competence" and "competence", competent approach, issues of professional competence development have been thoroughly studied.

In particular, A. Khutorsky believes that acquiring a set of theoretical knowledge for the requirements of putting the concept of "competence" into practice, solving specific tasks or situations, and solving the serious difficulties encountered in their implementation, is of great importance. [3]

I.A.Zimnyaya distinguishes three main groups of competence: - the competence of a person who is considered the subject of life activity; - competence related to human interactions with others; - competence manifested in all types and forms of human activity [4].

In particular, A. Tashanov explains that it is necessary to pay attention to three generalizing methods in the management competence system: organizational (interaction management), communicative (relationship management) and educational (development management). Management competence is seen as a process of implementation of specific activities of the management object and subject with stages: beginning, continuation (intensive or extensive growth, degradation, etc.), completion.

The procedural aspect of management competence assessment is based on showing its transitory characteristics: duration and stability of periods and stages. The following stages of management competence can be said: initial stage, the period when a person starts working as a manager, but has not mastered all aspects of management competence; the defined stage, the period when the leader is competent, when stable high results of the organization's activities are ensured. This stage, in turn, includes a set of descriptive indicators, internal and external criteria that differ from each other. [5]

G. Mintzberg explores important aspects of the formation process of civil servants.

He writes that, in short, "leaders force themselves to improve their skills, which means that they are incompetent." This qualification shows that "the leader is artificial and superficial", in order to avoid this, the leader must change his personality, take on various problems, work smoothly, avoid wasting time, focus only on useful and important work, and avoid getting deeply involved in general problems [6].

It can be seen that when a leader takes office, the quality and efficiency of his work depends on the effective use of time. The competence development process is influenced by many different factors, the behavior resulting from the organization's management system. In this case, we will have to study the internal and external conditions of the organization and the subjective personal character of the leader.

The head of a non-governmental non-profit organization must be fully aware of the customs and traditions of the area in which he lives, the ongoing reforms, have and know information about the development and characteristics of social thought, and at the same time use this information during his activities.

The head of a non-governmental, non-profit organization should know how to use the achievements of modern information and communication technologies, and in turn, work on existing collected information, information, analyze it, explain it and use it. Another important aspect of a competent approach in the process of globalization is that the representative of a non-governmental non-profit organization should always work independently on himself, constantly learn the latest information and communication technologies.

It is known that there are many social motivations in the effective management activity of the leader, including: successful achievement of the goal, self-development and freedom.

B. M. Teplov says that the professional's valuable and purposeful shell allows him to purposefully and meaningfully build his life, his activity in higher organizational systems, that is, the flourishing of his professional activity or this broken process (where the process and personal personality are together). A. Maslow, as the founder of the humanistic principles of management

theory, emphasizes that the feeling of desire and mission is the main universal description of self-activation in people [7].

It is known that the motivation of self-realization appears as a specific form of self-development, which arises on the basis of specific abilities of a leader and is directed to their implementation and development. For a leader, the main ones of such abilities are his initiative, entrepreneurship and organization, therefore, these determine the development of motivation. The formation of activities based on the motivation of self-realization is observed with clearly visible positive experiences and attitudes expressed to the work one is doing.

Competency modeling often uses the professionogram and profile method.

Professiogram is a description and definitions of psychological, industrial, technical, medical, hygiene and other important specialties, professions, which show the functions of this profession and represent the difficulties of mastering it. They are related to certain psychophysiological qualities of a person and production organization.

It expresses the scientifically based standards and requirements of the profession to the professional activity and personal qualities of the specialist. These requirements allow him to effectively perform his service duties, obtain the necessary product for society, and at the same time, create all the conditions for the development of the employee's personality.

The process of professional analysis of activity, as a rule, begins with familiarization with the organization's goals, structure and scheme of information networks. Then the information about the content of the activity from the point of view of both the performers and the leaders is collected. Typically, this method uses structured interviews with the executive and his immediate supervisor. It is important to plan the analyzed activity based on the results of the preliminary information collection and to conduct an examination of the obtained results. [8]

One of the important tasks is to develop the professional competence of the head of the non-governmental non-profit organization at the level of modern requirements, to form in them the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities, using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies.

To develop the perfect and continuous informational and methodological support for the development of the professional competence of the head of a non-governmental non-profit organization, to create the basis of the first scientific research conducted in this regard, to find ways to improve the professional competence of the heads of a non-governmental non-profit organization in the conditions of today's globalization and the high development of social opinion, as well as to provide them with methodological effective use of information and communication technologies in the way of assistance is considered important.

The Internet gives the leaders of non-governmental non-profit organizations the opportunity to receive various information about the management of our country and foreign society, distance courses, virtual conferences, professional communication, exchange of experience, etc., and to work on them. However, most employees of non-governmental non-profit organizations do not know how to find the necessary information and how to use Internet resources in their professional activities. Therefore, many activities related to the use of Internet networks are sometimes scattered and unstructured.

In general, the activities of the employees of non-governmental non-profit organizations on the Internet and the use of their created informational and methodical resources are not yet sufficient. Based on today's basic requirements of the society, the information and methodical

system aimed at improving the professional competence of the employees of non-governmental non-profit organizations has not been formed and is not scientifically and methodically based.

Therefore, it is important to develop the information and methodical system of foreign language teachers in the network in order to solve the problems related to the need to develop the professional competence of the heads of non-governmental non-profit organizations using ICT opportunities in the educational system and the lack of scientific and methodological basis for improving their professional competence. Currently, the rapid growth of the sphere of influence of information demands that people work on themselves in every way and that they become competitive, skillful and demanding personnel.

From this point of view, like the developed countries of the world, the personnel working in the system of non-governmental, non-commercial and other institutions of civil society in our country must have high knowledge in social, economic and political life and be competent in all respects.

If we analyze the above-mentioned points, professional competence is the definition of the personal qualities, goals and tasks of the head of a non-governmental non-profit organization, in turn, the ability to use modern information and communication technologies, and the addition of unique creative aspects, allows for a complete interpretation of this concept.

While researching the importance of information-methodological support in increasing the competence of non-governmental non-profit organization leaders and its specific features, "the professional competence of non-governmental non-profit organization leaders is his professional knowledge, personal qualities, the ability to define the goals and tasks of activity, the ability to use modern information and communication technologies and it is appropriate to say that it is a quality indicator that determines professional training.

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